

The Effect of Loneliness, and Depression on Internet Addiction in Students

Rahmah Ayuningtyas

tyara.tyass@gmail.com

Gunadarma University Faculty of Psychology

ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine how much influence loneliness and depression have on internet addiction in college students. Internet addiction in this study was measured by the adaptation scale of the Internet Addiction Test, loneliness in this study was measured by the De Jong Gierveld Loneliness Scale, and depression in this study was measured by the adaptation scale of the Self-Rating Depression Scale. Respondents in this study were 164 students who were still actively studying at Gunadarma University. This study uses multiple regression data analysis techniques using SPSS version 20 for Windows. The results of this study indicate that the effect of loneliness and depression on internet addiction is 10, 3% with a positive direction of relationship between loneliness and internet addiction and a negative direction of relationship between depression and internet addiction. This proves that there is an influence of loneliness and depression on internet addiction.

Keywords: Internet Addiction, Loneliness, and Depression

preliminary

Internet is not new anymore for most of the people of the World. Even children, teenagers and the elderly are actively using the internet. The internet itself is often used for social interaction, work, school assignments, but also the internet as a medium of entertainment such as online games, and watching videos, etc. Using the internet feels easy and fast, but using the internet itself is often bad if the user is already using the internet excessively (internet addiction). Normally, the average time spent online is six hours a day. However, a small percentage of people spend up to 10 hours a day, the majority of which are used to open social media sites. In Indonesia, internet users in 2014 reached 88.1 million. Teenagers

are the group with the highest internet access. Data from the Indonesian Internet Service Providers Association (APJII) and the UI Communication Study Center show that 49% of internet users are 14-25 years old (Triastuti, Primaldhi, & Rakhmani, 2014).

Internet addiction was first studied in 1996, and the findings were presented at the American Psychological Association. This study reviewed more than 600 cases of severe Internet users who showed clinical signs of addiction as measured by an adapted version of the DSM-IV criteria for pathological gambling (Young, 1996). According to Kathit and Singh (2014) internet addiction includes using excessive time or spending a large proportion of daily activities on the internet. According to Yong and Abrue (2011) Internet addicts displayed salience for activities, often experienced cravings and felt busy with the Internet while offline. Using the Internet as a way to escape disturbing feelings, develop tolerance for the Internet to achieve satisfaction, experience withdrawal when reducing Internet use, suffer from increased conflict with others due to activities, and relapse back to the Internet are also signs of addiction.

According to Demir and Kutlu (2016) individuals who experience deep feelings of loneliness have a high risk of internet addiction. It is also observed that individuals who are internet addicts display a tendency towards depression more than individuals who are not internet addicts. Yao and Zhong (2014) say that internet use is a maladaptive behavior that aims to reduce negative feelings such as loneliness, depression and social anxiety. Internet addiction has an empirical causal priority relationship with loneliness, excessive internet use will increase feelings of loneliness over time, not vice versa. In Karapetsas' research, Karapetsas, Zygoris, and Fotis (2015) stated that there is a direct relationship between loneliness and internet addiction. Saleem, Tufail, Khan, and Ismail (2015) said that internet addiction has a significant relationship with loneliness. The research of Pontes, Griffiths, and Patrão (2014) shows that high levels of internet addiction are more likely to own portable devices with Internet access,

use the internet for the hour, become lonely and socially lonely, perceive themselves as victims of bullying and cyberbullying in the classroom.

According to Oguz and Cakir (2014) in their research on prospective teachers, it can be seen that there is a positive relationship at the middle level between internet addiction and the level of loneliness of prospective teachers. According to Ozdemir, Kuzucu and Ark (2014), individuals with psychological problems are inherently at risk for addiction because their choice for online interaction is more than face-to-face communication. The risk for addiction among individuals was more significant when they used the Internet to deal with negative feelings such as sadness, anxiety or loneliness.

There are other factors besides loneliness, low resilience, and internet use that can influence internet addiction. Okwaraji, Aguwa, Onyebueke, and Eze (2015) stated that many young internet users are more at risk of becoming internet addicted than older users. This may be due to free time, lack of supervision by parents or caregivers. Male users were found to be internet addicted with depression related symptoms. According to Kathait and Singh (2014) Internet addiction has an effect on individual mental health and also focused gender differences between individuals on internet addiction. This is significantly associated with psychological symptoms such as depression, anxiety, social isolation and disturbed sleep patterns.

Accessing the internet is now easier to do with increasingly sophisticated mobile phones. Daily activities are also easy to share on internet social media through photos and writing. Individuals who have a big obsession with the number of likes or comments that exist through shared posts. If the obsession is not fulfilled, the individual can become depressed and feel ignored.

Andreou and Svoli (2012) depressed feelings of individuals who rely on the Internet for social support may persist or even worsen toward real-life interpersonal relationships, increasing the risk of becoming Internet addicted. Cheung and Wong (2011) in their study said that internet addicts in a sample of

adolescents displayed significant depressive symptoms. Meanwhile, in their research, Akin and Iskender (2011) stated that internet addiction directly affects depression, anxiety and stress. Students high in internet addiction are more likely to be susceptible to depression, anxiety and stress. Young and Rodger (1998) in their study showed that accurate assessment between depression and pathological Internet users can improve early detection, especially when one is hidden by the main symptoms of the other diagnosis.

Internet Addiction

According to the psychological dictionary of the American Psychology Association (APA) (2013) Internet addiction is a pattern of behavior characterized by excessive or obsessive use of online and offline computers that leads to suffering and distraction. According to Griffiths (1999) internet addiction is defined as addiction to operational technology which is a behavioral addiction involving humans and machines. According to Kuss, Griffiths, Karila, and Bilieux (in Kuss & Griffiths, 2015) Internet addiction has been conceptualized as addictive behavior involving excessive use of online applications and leading to a detrimental impact on the lives of affected individuals. Widyanto and McMurrin (in Young & Abreu, 2011) mention six components in internet addiction, namely

- a. Characteristics (Salience), is a special behavior that appears when an individual is accessing the internet and makes activities using the internet or online an important activity.
- b. Excessive use, which is excessive use of internet time that can lead to neglect of other things in order to use the internet longer.
- c. Neglect work, which is a disruption in the effectiveness of hours of delay on work and a decrease in the quality of work due to excessive internet use.
- d. Anticipation, is a state that is always waiting for time to access the internet.
- e. Lack of control, is a lack of control and an inability to control yourself in internet use.

f. Neglect of social life, is a condition when individuals leave their social life to use the internet.

Young (in the American Psychiatric Association, 2013) divides internet addiction into 3 levels, namely:

- a. Mild. At this level the individual is included in the average online user, the individual has control over their use. Internet usage at this level is less than 8 hours per day.
- b. Moderate. At this level, individuals often begin to experience several problems from using the internet. Internet usage at this rate is 8-10 hours per day.
- c. Severe. At this level individuals experience significant problems in their life. The internet is the most important thing so that it ignores other interests. Internet usage at this level exceeds 10 hours per day.

The factors that influence internet addiction (Young, Pistner, O'Mara & Buchanan, 1998) are: gender, psychological conditions, socioeconomic conditions, the purpose and time of internet use. From these influencing factors, the researcher focuses on psychological conditions that can affect internet addiction. Because internet addiction can affect a person's psychological conditions such as depression and anxiety disorders, so often individuals are more comfortable when interacting online than offline.

Loneliness

According to Margalit (1994) variability in the definition of loneliness seems to reflect differences in imagining the nature of social deprivation experienced by lonely people in their environment. Woodward's (in Margalit, 1994) says that loneliness is a feeling of being alone and disconnected or alienated from positive people, places and things. Peplau and Perlman (in Peplau, 1988) say that loneliness is a painful warning signal that a person's social relationships are deficient in several important ways. According to Gierveld, Tilburg, and Dykstra (2006) loneliness is a situation experienced by an individual as one in which there

is a lack of unpleasant or unacceptable (quality) certain relationships. This includes situations,

According to Weiss (in Margalit, 1994), although different individuals may emphasize various dimensions of their personal experiences of social and emotional isolation, constructing components is seen as clearly linked experiences rather than as different

- a. Emotional loneliness. The dimension of emotional loneliness refers to deficiencies in socio-emotional bonds and intimate relationships with others and can be seen as leading to feelings of anxiety and isolation.
- b. Social loneliness (Social loneliness), refers to a lack of recognized social roles and a lack of social network of relationships, can be characterized by feelings of boredom, aimlessness, and depression.

Depression

According to the clinical psychology dictionary of the American Psychology Association (APA) (2013) Depression is a normal mood fluctuation ranging from unhappiness and dissatisfaction to feelings of extreme sadness, pessimism, and hopelessness. Borrill (2000) says that in depression, this word is used to describe a variety of moods - from low spirits to severe problems that plague everyday life. The individual feels sad or angry, is hopeless about the future, may have a change in appetite, has trouble sleeping or waking up, feels overwhelmed and feels guilty or even thinks about death or suicide. According to Atkinson, Atkinson, and Hilgard (1993) depression is considered abnormal when the depression is out of control and continues until the time when most people have recovered. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), (2012) depression is a common mental disorder that presents with a depressed mood, loss of interest or pleasure, decreased energy, feelings of guilt or low self-esteem, disturbed sleep or appetite, and poor concentration. Additionally, depression often comes with symptoms of anxiety. Kantor (1992) says that normal depression has clear thinking about defenses and thoughts that are slowed down or reduced.

According to Zung (in Robinson, Shaver, & Wrightsman, 1991) there are four categories of depressive symptoms, namely

- a. Components of Affective-Psychic Disorders, Physical affective disorders are disorders related to one's emotions or feelings and thoughts.
- b. Components of Physiological Disorders, Physiological disorders are disorders related to the function of the condition of the body, tissues or organs, as well as the chemical and physical processes involved.
- c. Psychomotor disorders, psychomotor disorders are disorders in the control of psychological movements.
- d. Psychological Disorders Index, Psychological disorders are a reflection of normal mood fluctuations, which may indicate early symptoms of a depressive episode in an individual.

Hypothesis

There are effects of loneliness and depression on internet addiction.

Research methods

Population and Sample

The population in this study were 500 students of Gunadarma University, Faculty of Psychology, class 2013-2014, studying in the Bekasi area. The sampling technique in this study used a quota sampling technique. Quota sampling is a sampling technique by selecting samples that have certain characteristics up to the desired sample quota. The sample in this study were students of Gunadarma University, Faculty of Psychology, class of 2013 - 2014, located in the Bekasi area. There are 164 students sampled, consisting of male and female psychology students at Gunadarma University studying in the Bekasi area.

Data collection technique

Data collection was carried out using instruments or measuring instruments in the form of a questionnaire consisting of an Internet Addiction Test consisting of 39 internet addiction items with characteristic components (alpha cronbach

0.733), excessive use (alpha cronbach 0.749), job neglect (alpha cronbach 0.750) , anticipation (Cronbach's alpha 0.492), lack of control (Cronbach's alpha 0.482), social neglect (Cronbach's alpha 0.489). De Jong Gierveld Loneliness Scale which consists of 11 items of loneliness with dimensions of emotional loneliness (alpha cronbach 0.751) and social loneliness (alpha cronbach 0.785). And the Self-Rating Depression Scale (SDS) consists of 26 depression items (alpha cronbach 0.840). To determine the effect of loneliness and depression on internet addiction in students, then testing the hypothesis in this study using multiple regression data analysis techniques. Data analysis was performed with the help of SPSS for Windows software.

Results and Discussion

Table 1.1. Research Results The Effect of Loneliness and Depression on Internet Addiction

Variable	β	Significance	F	Significance	R	R ²
Regression			8,979	0.001	0.317	0.100
Lonely	0.178	0.045				
Depression	-0.185	0.037				

* p <0.050

This study aims to examine the effect of loneliness and depression on internet addiction. The test results from the multiple regression analysis show that the hypothesis is accepted. The effective contribution of loneliness and depression to internet addiction is 10.0%, where the remaining 90.0% is another factor affecting variables outside the study. This is shown by the effect of internet addiction on loneliness and depression 8.979 with a significance value of 0.001 (p <0.010) which means that loneliness and depression have a significant effect on internet addiction. With an r value of 0.178 with a significance of 0.045 on loneliness on internet addiction, this means that there is a positive and significant relationship between loneliness and internet addiction. Meanwhile, depression and internet addiction in the study had an r value of -0.185 with a significance of 0.037, this means that there is a negative and significant relationship between

depression and internet addiction. This proves that there is an effect of loneliness and depression on internet addiction, so it can be said that the hypothesis in this study is accepted.

The effect of loneliness and depression in this study has an effective contribution of 10.0% to internet addiction. Whereas in Ayas and Horzum's (2013) study the influence of depression, loneliness, and self-esteem had an effective contribution of 14.0% to internet addiction. Where the relationship between depression ($r: 0.190, p < 0.05$), and loneliness ($r: 0.130, p < 0.05$) has a positive and significant relationship with internet addiction, while the variable self-esteem ($r: 0.020, p > 0.05$) has no effect on internet addiction.

It can be said that loneliness has a significant and positive effect on internet addiction, with a correlation value of $r = 0.714$ and $p = 0.049$ ($p < 0.050$). The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Bozoglan, Demirer, and Sahin (2013) show that loneliness has a significant correlation with internet addiction ($r = 0.61; p < 0.05$) which states that there is a positive relationship between loneliness and internet addiction. This is because individuals who have high loneliness have a high addiction to the internet too.

Meanwhile, depression has a significant and negative effect on internet addiction, namely the correlation value $r = -0.193$ and $p = 0.029$. In contrast to the results of previous studies which are significantly positive from Akin and Iskander (2011) with a significant value ($r = 0.672, p < 0.01$) which indicates that depression has a significant impact on internet addiction and addiction.

In this study depression has an influence on internet addiction but has a negative direction. Where when individuals have high depression they are not addicted to the internet, and vice versa when individuals have low depression they are addicted to the internet. This is because when individuals are depressed they prefer to do activities with other people (such as family or playmates). Even though they consider the use of the internet to be important, they choose to be close to the people around them.

Weaknesses of Research

In this study, the use of the internet addiction scale on the components of anticipation, lack of control, and neglect of social life has a reliability value of less than 0.700. So that the components of anticipation, lack of control, and neglect of social life are considered unreliable. In addition, descriptive testing of internet addiction is based on the duration of internet use, where the most researched subjects fall into the category of 4-6 hours / day. Based on Young's internet addiction category (in the American Psychiatric Association, 2013) the duration of 4 - 6 hours / day is included in the category of mild internet addiction where daily use is less than 8 hours / day, and cannot be said to be included in the subject of internet addiction.

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